

THE STRUCTURE OF THE TUTOR'S PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES AND THE ESSENCE OF THEIR FUNCTIONS

¹Ibraimov Xolboy Ibragimovich, ²Urinova Nilufar Mukhammadovna

¹Director of the Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after T.N.Kori Niyozzi, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor.

²FarSU Associated professor, Candidate of pedagogical sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10205678>

Abstract. *This article describes the tutor's responsibilities in the development of a student's personality, the content of the functions and competencies that he should possess.*

Keywords: *tutor, student, tutor duties, functions, competencies.*

In order for each person to find his place in society, he must first develop and mature as a person. After all, only a member of the society who is psychologically developed, who can be an example to others with his individual characteristics and behavior, who has a broad worldview, who can put the interests of the country and the Motherland above his own personal benefit. can be a person with a nickname. Special attention is paid to the personal development of our students during their higher education, which is a manifestation of the government's attention to the issue of youth in our country.

From the first days of our independence, the issue of youth has risen to the level of state policy. In particular, on September 9, 2021, the adoption of Cabinet of Ministers decision No. 563 "On measures to increase the level of accommodation for students in the higher education institutions of the Republic" was aimed at further improving the conditions created for our students. . In the decision - to provide students with affordable housing, but with all amenities; quality and safety guaranteed to students - delivery of high-quality food products at low prices; Within the framework of the 1st-3rd courses of the bachelor's degree, a number of systematic conveniences and opportunities, which have been designed for a long time in higher education, such as the appointment of a "tutor" position at the expense of 1 staff unit for every 120-150 students [1] were established.

The new term "tutor" has been adopted into our speech from the English language, and it expresses the meaning of a person who acts as a teacher and trainer. The position of tutor was abolished from September 1, 2021, when the "group coach" institution for working with students was abolished, and instead of it, workers working with students and young people were established as tutors. The holder of this position, in the literal sense, ensures the integral connection of the student with the education system; the ability of the student to show his potential during the educational process, to have a deep understanding of himself, his identity, his worldview, to consciously control his activities, to make the right decisions regarding the systematic management of his behavior a person who develops skills and abilities. It helps students to consciously understand the consequences of each activity and action, to find ways to ensure the fulfillment of their dreams in life [1].

The effectiveness of the tutor's activity is measured by the increase of the student's internal desire to study and the transformation of education into an effective process. Literally, the effectiveness of the educational process in the higher education system is ensured by the cooperation of "professor - teacher - student - tutor". Naturally, a highly educated person holding

the position of a tutor, i.e. as a coach, mentor, specialist in the field in which the student is studying, is pedagogically, psychologically, ethically, aesthetically perfect, self-aware, broad-minded, sane, intellectual. should be capable.

The activities of tutors, who are intended to work in the higher education system in the areas of spiritual-educational and moral-educational, educational and teaching-methodical, scientific, innovative and scientific-research, are world education. not new to the lim system. A tutor's relationship with students - teaching and ensuring its quality is related to a number of tutoring tasks:

- 1) The tutor organizes an individual work process with students - determines, diagnoses, forms and develops their knowledge;
- 2) organizes their personal support during the educational process;
- 3) Coordinates information search and self-education for students;
- 4) Accompanies the process of student personality formation (by him - can understand and form successes and failures, give personal order to the educational process, create goals for the future);
- 5) formulates goals together with the student and evaluates all kinds of resources for implementation;
- 6) Coordinates the interdependence of cognitive interests with students, determines the directions and methodology of education, given science and orientation courses, information and advisory work, career guidance systems, chooses the optimal organizational structure for this;
- 7) Helps the student to consciously choose educational strategies, overcoming problems and difficulties, self-education [2,133].

Based on the analysis of international experience and pedagogical and psychological sources, we have distinguished the following functions of the tutor:

- Management function;
- Diagnostic function;
- Goal setting function;
- Motivational function;
- Planning function;
- Communicative function;
- Reflexive function;
- Methodological function [6,63].

Unlike the activity of a teacher, the activity of a tutor is more related to the purposeful development of students' cognitive independence.

This situation requires the mastery of the management function and includes the following specific actions:

- 1) The tutor determines the characteristics and purpose of his activity and student activity;
- 2) Monitoring the progress of students' activities;
- 3) Assessing the appropriateness of cognitive activity, students learn the desired aspect of this activity;
- 4) Evaluation of the results of tutor-training interaction throughout the educational process;
- 5) Development of solutions for changing educational activities;

6) Implementation of decisions on changing and stimulating cognitive activity of students;

7) Implementation of actions that can change the students' own activities, as well as the situation.

In a broad sense, the management function includes: correction and evaluation.

The tutor performs the following tasks through the control function:

- analyzing students' tasks, determining the level of success of education and training;
- assessment of the quality of performed tasks;
- correction of students' activities and tasks in accordance with the results of the inspection process;
- task monitoring [3,10].

The diagnostic function is related to the analysis of student behavior. This function allows you to evaluate the positive and negative aspects of student performance.

In the work of the tutor, this function is manifested as follows:

- studying preliminary information about students;
- identification of individual characteristics, training (learning style, type of thinking, development of abilities, etc.);
- to determine students' needs, motives, hopes, fears and their causes in order to ensure the effectiveness of teaching;
- identifying knowledge, skills and experiences, as well as studying and analyzing the reasons for success or failure;
- diagnosis of the mastery level of the course studied by students.

The goal setting function is the basis of the tutor's work. The tutor should formulate long-term and short-term educational and training goals.

To implement the goal setting function, the tutor solves the following problems:

- analysis of the goals of the educational model;
- to determine the content and specific features of educational activities;
- participates in the determination of personal qualities, difficulties and problems that the student faces in his work;
- formation of expected results, working with active students (what they should know, what they should do and how they should be);
- coordination of set goals with educational goals;
- coordination of goals with the capabilities of students.

The motivational task of the tutor is to create:

- to ensure that students join interesting learning and courses in the course. To use this function, you must be able to solve the following problems:
- to determine the initial expectations, personal needs and motivations of students from education;
- formation of effective, mainly independent activity;
- creating an environment of interest and confidence;
- stimulating learning motivation with different teaching methods.

The planning function is to create an individual development program. Based on the students and their goals and ways to achieve the goals, the individual development program of

students is drawn up with the help of a tutor. Effective planning of the educational process requires the skills of the tutor, in which:

- formation of four-stage educational goals - analysis of the specialist's development model (what he should know, what competencies and qualities he should have) and preliminary diagnostic results (educational needs, their initial training level, professional experience, etc.) is carried out taking into account;

- actively forming one's strategy and tactics with students;
- it is necessary to determine the sequence of actions with the goals and expected results set according to the model.

Communicative function of the tutor. This feature is primarily important when the tutor is interacting with students.

The following requirements apply to the implementation of this function:

- being open with students;
- to understand and implement the following requirements in their activities:
"All students are the same, all students are different";
- establishing working and partnership relations between himself and students.

The role of the reflexive function in the activity of the tutor is very large. Reflection is the semantic center of the person and the mechanism of human development. Therefore, the tutor will have the opportunity to develop individually and professionally during the implementation of this function. Reflection - should be focused on the goals and content of the course, technologies, its embodiment in the educational process, achieved results (their compliance with the goals, measures of this compliance, etc.), character and means of communication, communication style, etc. On the other hand, the subject of reflection is the method of changing one's activity, communication and thinking.

Therefore, the reflection function is implemented in the following activity tasks:

- Organization of the analysis of tutor opportunities;
- shields for reflecting on one's own activities and identifying the tutor's individual styles (the ideas and principles that the tutor gives to the management - in this case, the preferred teaching style, etc.), his difficulties, mistakes and achievements;
- reflections on creating "reasons" in problematic situations in students' activities;
- understanding the problem place in students' activities, the difficulties that caused them and their elimination - constitutes reflection.

Methodological function of the tutor is one of the important ones.

Features that make up this feature include:

- creation of necessary tools and process for organizing education (special assignments, sets of questions, problem situations, visual materials, etc.);
- development of various diagnostic methods - control questions, questionnaires, questionnaire lists, information cards, test materials, etc.;
- analyze and describe his tutoring experience;
- to introduce the effective experience of other tutors into their work.

The tutor's wide field of activity allows to show the person from different sides. All considered tutor functions serve to develop professional competence.

The professional competence of the tutor is the main component of his professionalism. It shows the theoretical and practical training of the tutor in a harmonious way. If professional

competence is not formed, the tutor cannot perform his activities at the required level. According to the existing approaches, the tutor's professionalism represents his intellectual, emotional, motor-willed state in a holistic way. Because these cases embody all directions of the tutor's activity. Especially his professional growth and skills are evident in this system[4,115].

Many experts emphasize that the professional image of a tutor is manifested through his abilities. The manifestation of the tutor's professional abilities is reflected in their ability to realize the talents of students and educate them at the level of modern ethical requirements. They include: being able to correctly assess students' inner states and experiences, being a role model for students, instilling feelings of benevolence and gratitude in students, knowing the means to satisfy their aspirations and desires, identifying the unique aspects and talents of students. taking into account the ability to have an educational and educational impact on them, to strengthen students' self-confidence, to find the necessary methods of communicating with them, to introduce students' self-respect possible

In conclusion, it is worth saying that today there are a wide range of opportunities that serve to develop the activity of a tutor. Accordingly, the professional competences formed by the tutors will help them gain international experience.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining “Respublika Oliy ta’lim muassasalarida talabalarni turar joy bilan qamrab olish darajasini oshirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida” gi 563-sonli qarori, Davlat oliy ta’lim muassasalarida tyutorlik faoliyatini tashkil etish tartibi to‘g‘risidagi “Namunaviy nizom”. 10.09.2021. Farmon//lex.uz.
2. Верховина А.В., Тьютор как педагогическая специальность в системе профессионального образования.-М.: Студенческий вестник, 2015.- 133с.
3. Габдулхаков В.Ф. Тьюторинг творческой деятельности: компоненты педагогической технологии. Монография. – Казань, 2013. – 9-14 с.
4. Кокамбо, Ю.Д. Тьюторство как новая форма взаимодействия участников образовательного Вестник Амурского государственного университета. Сер. Гуманитарные науки. – 2013. – Вып. 60. – 110-115 с.
5. Urinova, N. M., & Abdullaeva, N. (2021). Opportunities to use project-based teaching technology in the development of students’ research competence. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 2344-2348
6. Urinova Nilufar Mukhammadovna. (2023). IMPLEMENTATION OF TUTOR’S SUPPORT MODEL IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 4(03), 58–64. <https://doi.org/10.37547/pedagogics-crjp-04-03-12>
7. O‘rinova Nilufar Muhammadovna. (2023). Xorijiy ta’limda tyutorlik faoliyatining mohiyati va funksiyalari.FarDU.Ilmiy Xabarlar.3, 2-5.
8. Ibraimov Kh. I. Creativity as one of the characteristics of the personality of the future teacher // *Science, education and culture*. – 2018. – no. 3 (27). - P. 44-46.
9. Ibragimovich Kh.I. Peculiarities of using credit-module technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan // *Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal*. - 2021. - P. 209-214.

10. Ibraimov Kh. "Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system." *International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education* 1 (2020): 6-15.
11. Ibragimov, X., Abdullayeva Sh. "Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)." T.: Fan va texnologiya 288 (2008).
12. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –T., “Shaffof”, 2023, 416-bet.
13. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
14. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
15. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." *Вопросы науки и образования* 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
16. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
17. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.
18. Ibragimov, X. I., U. A. Yo'ldoshev, and X. Bobomirzayev. "Pedagogik psixologiya." O'quv qo'llanma. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashiriyoti Toshkent (2009).